

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**RESISTANCE TO TOPICAL ANTIMICROBIAL
MEDICATIONS: REVIEW ARTICLE**Nehad J. Ahmed^{1*}¹Clinical Pharmacy Department, College of Pharmacy, Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz
University, Alkharj, Saudi Arabia**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019**Abstract:**

Introduction: antibiotic-resistance is considered one of the main public health problems. The leading cause for antimicrobial resistance is the unsuitable usage of antimicrobials.

Methodology: The methodology includes searching PubMed, using the key word (topical antibiotic) AND (resistance), the search was limited to include only clinical trials during the last 10 years.

Results: Many infections don't need using antimicrobials systemically and can be treated with a topical antimicrobial. Topical antibiotics has some side effects and probable resistance has developed against it. As a result, the researchers start searching for new topical antimicrobials to decrease the bacterial resistance.

Conclusion:

Bacterial resistance lead to many negative outcomes, this resistance can occur by using systemic or topical antibiotics, so it is important to use antibiotics only when needed and the patients should follow the recommendations that were given by the health care providers. It is important to increase the awareness about the bacterial resistance.

Keywords: Resistance, topical, Antimicrobial

Corresponding author:**Nehad J. Ahmed,**

Clinical Pharmacy Department, College of Pharmacy,

Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University,

Alkharj, Saudi Arabia

n.ahmed@psau.edu.sa, Mobile: 0096654370780

QR code

Please cite this article in press Nehad J. Ahmed., **Resistance To Topical Antimicrobial Medications: Review Article.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

BACKGROUND:

Antibiotic-resistance is considered one of the main public health problems. At least 2 million individuals are infected with antibiotic-resistant germs in the united states yearly. Bacterial resistance results in decreasing the efficacy of antimicrobials, rising the hospital stays, rising doctor visits, and increasing the cost of the treatment. (1) The leading cause for decreasing the usefulness of antimicrobials due to antimicrobial resistance is the unsuitable usage of antimicrobials. (2)

METHODOLOGY:

The review methodology includes searching PubMed, (3) using the key word (topical antibiotic) AND (resistance) , the search was limited to include clinical trials during the last 10 years excluding other types of study and excluded the studies on animals.

RESULTS:

Many infections don't need using antimicrobials systemically and can be treated with a topical antimicrobial , such as the usage of mupirocin in the management of Impetigo. (4) and for the eradication of nasal meticillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* but the resistance for this topical drug has been reported. (5) As a result, topical antibiotics should not be used alone for long-lasting therapy to avoid multi-resistance. (6)

The researchers start searching for new antimicrobials used topically to decrease the bacterial resistance such as the usage of Staphefekt in the management of Atopic dermatitis . Totté, J et al reported that there is lack of resistance for Staphefekt or other endolysins. (7) Moreover, The prolonged use of topical antibiotics rises the antibiotic resistance, for example the prolonged use of fusidic acid in patients with atopic dermatitis repeatedly developed a fusidic acid-resistant clone of *S. aureus* as reported by Thum, D et al. (8)

Many other studies were focused on the management of acne vulgaris, one study stated that there should be an alternative effective treatment with good safety profile due to increased bacterial resistance to topical antibiotics such as Silver nanoparticle gel. (9) another study suggested the usage of topical dapson 5% gel for long-term acne maintenance therapy because it can be used efficiently without the possibility of emerging antibiotic resistance. (10)

Irolomoni, G reported that Fusidic acid is very active against Gram-positive bacteria and the resistance rates to fusidic acid are steadily low. (11)

The first line for the treatment of all forms of leishmaniasis is meglumine antimoniate which is also used topically. Unfortunately, this medication has some severe side effects and probable resistance has developed against it. (12)

There are many others topical antibiotics available such as furasol that is used as a therapy for sore throat gargle solution , its use did not lead to bacterial resistance. (13) another example is tyrothricin 0.1% that is used to treat acne . Tyrothricin is less effective than other medications but still it is considered alternative approach in the management of mild to severe acne papulopustulosa because it is more tolerable than other agents and it is not known to cause resistance (14)

Lee, J stated that the recent usage of topical fluoroquinolone during ocular surgery and hospitalization were significantly associated with increasing fluoroquinolone resistance in *S. aureus* isolates from ocular culture and in patients with positive coagulase negative staphylococcus. (15)

Olsen WM, et al stated that in order to decrease resistance LTX-109 which is a fast-acting bactericidal antimicrobial can be used for topical treatment. It can prevent infections by MSSA/MRSA during hospitalization with a low propensity of resistance development.(16)

Johnson DW et al studied the use of honey for the prevention of peritoneal-dialysis-related infections and reported that antibacterial honey is an innovative, inexpensive and effective prophylactic agent used topically without making microbial resistance. (17)

Other study reported that retapamulin is a topical agent that has a clinical success rates higher than placebo in the management of patients with secondarily infected traumatic lesions but can cause resistance. (18) Mupirocin is topical antibiotics can be used as a prophylactic to reduce peritoneal catheter exit site infection risk but causes antibiotic resistance as reported by Findlay, A et al. (19)

Additionally, many fluoroquinolones ophthalmic antibiotics can be used in treated infections such as endophthalmitis, but the developing resistance of ocular pathogens to fluoroquinolones may decrease their repetitive use. (20-22)

Retapamulin 1% ointment is considered a convenient and effective agent and its risk for development of bacterial resistance is low (23). Ozkan, J studied the Effect of Prophylactic Antibiotic Drops on Ocular Microbiota and reported

that antibiotic use decreased microbiota on lids but didn't affect the microbiota of the throat or change bacterial resistance to tobramycin. (24)

Lovino, S. M stated that bacterial resistance making mupirocin, fusidic acid, and erythromycin ineffective for the treatment of impetigo. Different agents such as NVC-422 (*N, N*-dichloro-2, 2-dimethyltaurine) can be used, this agent kills pathogens without the development of resistance. (25)

Staphylococcus epidermidis developed resistance to third-generation, fourth-generation fluoroquinolones, trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole, gentamicin, clindamycin, macrolides and to doxycycline as reported by Dave, S et al. (26)

The bacterial resistance can be decreased by using combinations of topical agents as reported by Pazoki-Toroudi H. (27) Topical antibiotic ointments are usually used for the post procedural management of superficial wounds but these agents may not be necessary for the treatment of clean surgical wounds because of the development of allergic contact dermatitis and drug resistance. (28,29)

Kim, S et al demonstrated substantial levels of resistance to third- and fourth-generation fluoroquinolones and multi-resistance amongst patients with choroidal neovascularization. (30)

Another study confirmed the very good topical acceptability of the kanamycin eye ointment. It is a wide spectrum of antibiotics can be used to avoid the development of resistance so it is a good option for ophthalmological infections. (31) Aykut S stated that infection risk attributable to methicillin- and mupirocin-resistant coagulase-negative staphylococcus should be kept in mind. (32)

Jackson JM reported that the use of combined clindamycin phosphate 1%/benzoyl peroxide 5% gel reduces the emergence of antimicrobial resistance. (33)

de Leeuw, J stated that increasing awareness on the adverse effects of topical and systemic drugs that are used in the treatment of acne vulgaris by health care providers and patients and increasing antibiotic resistance of *Propionibacterium acnes* have eased the way for a search into new safe and efficacious treatment approaches such as the use of photodynamic therapy. (34)

He, L et al reported that Prophylactic topical moxifloxacin 0.5% starting 1 day before ocular surgery lead to a significant rise in fluoroquinolone-resistant bacteria. (35)

Dhawan SS reported that in order to decrease the development of *Propionibacterium acnes* antibiotic resistance it is important to add benzoyl peroxide to antibiotic therapy. (36)

Johnson DW et al reported that honey may represent a suitable alternative method of chemoprophylaxis in patients with central venous catheters due to its low tendency to promote antimicrobial resistance. (37)

Daly, J reported that in ICUs, the use of selective oropharyngeal decontamination regimen is preferable to the selective digestive tract decontamination regimen since it involves a lower volume of topical antibiotics, thus reducing the possibility of developing antibiotic resistance in the long term. (38)

Lipsky, B studied the use of topical and systemic antimicrobials for treating mildly infected diabetic foot ulcers and stated that topical pexiganan might be an alternative to oral therapy and might decrease the possibility of selecting antimicrobial-resistant bacteria. (39)

Denis, F studied the microbiologic efficacy of using azithromycin 1.5% eye drops for the management of purulent bacterial conjunctivitis for three days and reported that some bacteria were classified as resistant to tested antibiotics, nevertheless, eradication was observed, these results give prominence to the specific pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics of the ocular route. (40)

CONCLUSION:

Bacterial resistance lead to many negative outcomes such as decreasing the efficacy of antimicrobials. The leading cause for antimicrobial resistance is the inappropriate usage of antimicrobials. This resistance can occur by using systemic or topical antibiotics, so it is important to use antibiotics only when needed and the patients should follow the recommendations that were given by the health care providers. It is important to increase the awareness of the healthcare professionals and the patients about the bacterial resistance. Additionally, Topical antibiotics should not be used as monotherapy and also topical and oral antibiotics should never be used concurrently.

REFERENCES:

1. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2019). *CDC Works 24/7*. [online] Available at: <https://www.cdc.gov/> [Accessed 18 Apr. 2019].
2. Idsociety.org. (2019). *IDSA Home*. [online] Available at: <https://www.idsociety.org/> [Accessed 18 Apr. 2019].

3. Ncbi.nlm.nih.gov. (2019). *Home - PubMed - NCBI*. [online] Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed> [Accessed 18 Apr. 2019].
4. Armstrong, C. (2019). *IDSA Releases Guidelines for the Diagnosis and Treatment of Skin and Soft Tissue Infections*. [online] Aafp.org. Available at: <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2006/1001/p1215.html> [Accessed 18 Apr. 2019].
5. Poovelikunnel, T., Gethin, G., Solanki, D., McFadden, E., Codd, M. and Humphreys, H. (2018). Randomized controlled trial of honey versus mupirocin to decolonize patients with nasal colonization of meticillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Journal of Hospital Infection*, 98(2), pp.141-148.
6. Ma, Y., Zhang, N., Wu, S., Huang, H. and Cao, Y. (2016). Antimicrobial activity of topical agents against *Propionibacterium acnes*: an in vitro study of clinical isolates from a hospital in Shanghai, China. *Frontiers of Medicine*, 10(4), pp.517-521.
7. Totté, J., de Wit, J., Pardo, L., Schuren, F., van Doorn, M. and Pasmans, S. (2017). Targeted anti-staphylococcal therapy with endolysins in atopic dermatitis and the effect on steroid use, disease severity and the microbiome: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial (MAAS trial). *Trials*, 18(1).
8. Thum, D., Seidl, H., Hein, R., Ring, J., Andres, C. and Mempel, M. (2013). Current resistance patterns of *Staphylococcus aureus* towards topical antibiotics and relevant antiseptics in patients with atopic dermatitis and impetigo. *JDDG: Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft*, 11(9), pp.875-878.
9. Natthachat Jurairattanaporn, Thep Chalermchai, Suwirakorn Ophaswongse, Montree Udompataikul. (2017). Comparative Trial of Silver Nanoparticle Gel and 1% Clindamycin Gel when Use in Combination with 2.5% Benzoyl Peroxide in Patients with Moderate Acne Vulgaris. *J Med Assoc Thai* 100(1), PP. 78-85
10. Leon H. Kircik (2016). Use of Dapsone 5% Gel as Maintenance Treatment of Acne Vulgaris Following Completion of Oral Doxycycline and Dapsone 5% Gel Combination Treatment *J Drugs Dermatol* 15(2), PP.191-195
11. irolomoni, G., Mattina, R., Manfredini, S., Vertuani, S. and Fabrizi, G. (2016). Fusidic acid betamethasone lipid cream. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 70, pp.4-13.
12. Rajabi, O., Layegh, P., Hashemzadeh, S. and Khoddami, M. (2016). Topical liposomal azithromycin in the treatment of acute cutaneous leishmaniasis. *Dermatologic Therapy*, 29(5), pp.358-363.
13. Nosulya, E., Kim, I., Chernykh, N. and Karnoukhova, O. (2015). Acute tonsillopharyngitis: the effectiveness of topical therapy. *Vestnik otorinolaringologii*, 80(5), p.71.
14. Richter, C., Trojahn, C., Hillmann, K., Dobos, G., Stroux, A., Kottner, J. and Blume-Peytavi, U. (2015). Reduction of Inflammatory and Noninflammatory Lesions with Topical Tyrothricin 0.1% in the Treatment of Mild to Severe Acne Papulopustulosa: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial. *Skin Pharmacology and Physiology*, 29(1), pp.1-8.
15. Lee, J. and Choi, S. (2015). Risk Factors for Fluoroquinolone Resistance in Ocular Cultures. *Korean Journal of Ophthalmology*, 29(1), p.7.
16. Olsen WM, et al. 2011. LTX-109 is an effective, novel agent for nasal decolonization of MRSA/MSSA—results from a phase I/IIa study, abstr. L1-275. Abstr. 51st Intersci. Conf. Antimicrob. Agents Chemother
17. Johnson, D., Badve, S., Pascoe, E., Beller, E., Cass, A., Clark, C., de Zoysa, J., Isbel, N., McTaggart, S., Morrish, A., Playford, E., Scaria, A., Snelling, P., Vergara, L. and Hawley, C. (2014). Antibacterial honey for the prevention of peritoneal-dialysis-related infections (HONEYPOT): a randomised trial. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 14(1), pp.23-30.
18. Tomayko, J., Li, G., Breton, J., Scangarella-Oman, N., Dalessandro, M. and Martin, M. (2013). The Safety and Efficacy of Topical Retapamulin Ointment Versus Placebo Ointment in the Treatment of Secondarily Infected Traumatic Lesions. *Advances in Skin & Wound Care*, 26(3), pp.113-121.
19. Findlay, A., Serrano, C., Punzalan, S. and Fan, S. (2013). Increased Peritoneal Dialysis Exit Site Infections Using Topical Antiseptic Polyhexamethylene Biguanide Compared to Mupirocin: Results of a Safety Interim Analysis of an Open-Label Prospective Randomized Study. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, 57(5), pp.2026-2028.
20. Ray, K., Prajna, L., Srinivasan, M., Geetha, M., Karpagam, R., Glidden, D., Oldenburg, C., Sun, C., McLeod, S., Acharya, N. and Lietman, T. (2013). Fluoroquinolone Treatment and Susceptibility of Isolates From Bacterial Keratitis. *JAMA Ophthalmology*, 131(3), p.310.
21. Haas, W., Gearing, L., Hesje, C., Sanfilippo, C. and Morris, T. (2012). Microbiological Etiology and Susceptibility of Bacterial Conjunctivitis Isolates from Clinical Trials with Ophthalmic, Twice-Daily Besifloxacin. *Advances in Therapy*, 29(5), pp.442-455.
22. Cernak, M., Majtanova, N., Cernak, A. and Majtan, J. (2011). Honey Prophylaxis Reduces the Risk of Endophthalmitis During Perioperative Period of Eye

- Surgery. *Phytotherapy Research*, 26(4), pp.613-616.
23. Kircik LH (2012). Efficacy and tolerability of retapamulin 1% ointment for the treatment of infected atopic dermatitis: a pilot study. *J Drugs Dermatol*, 11(7), pp.858-60.
 24. Ozkan, J., Zhu, H., Gabriel, M., Holden, B. and Willcox, M. (2012). Effect of Prophylactic Antibiotic Drops on Ocular Microbiota and Physiology during Silicone Hydrogel Lens Wear. *Optometry and Vision Science*, 89(3), pp.326-335.
 25. Iovino, S. M., Krantz, K. D., Blanco, D. M., Fernández, J. A., Ocampo, N., Najafi, A., ... Anderson, M. (2011). NVC-422 topical gel for the treatment of impetigo. *International journal of clinical and experimental pathology*, 4(6), 587-595.
 26. Dave, S., Toma, H. and Kim, S. (2011). Ophthalmic Antibiotic Use and Multidrug-Resistant Staphylococcus epidermidis. *Ophthalmology*, 118(10), pp.2035-2040.
 27. Pazoki-Toroudi, H., Nilforoushzadeh, M., Ajami, M., Jaffary, F., Aboutaleb, N., Nassiri-Kashani, M. and Firooz, A. (2011). Combination of azelaic acid 5% and clindamycin 2% for the treatment of acne vulgaris. *Cutaneous and Ocular Toxicology*, 30(4), pp.286-291.
 28. Tanghetti, E. (2012). Treatment of minor wounds from dermatologic procedures: a comparison of three topical wound care ointments using a laser wound model. *Yearbook of Dermatology and Dermatologic Surgery*, 2012, pp.509-510.
 29. Michaels, B. and Del Rosso, J. (2012). A comparison of postprocedural wound care treatments: Do antibiotic-based ointments improve outcomes?. *Yearbook of Dermatology and Dermatologic Surgery*, 2012, pp.292-293.
 30. Kim, S., Toma, H., Midha, N., Cherney, E., Recchia, F. and Doherty, T. (2010). Antibiotic Resistance of Conjunctiva and Nasopharynx Evaluation Study: A Prospective Study of Patients Undergoing Intravitreal Injections. *Ophthalmology*, 117(12), pp.2372-2378.
 31. C. Jürgens, S. Leicher, S. Antal, J. Giebel, F. H. Tost (2010). On the topical tolerance of aminoglycoside antibiotics--a prospective comparative cytomorphological study. *Klin Monatsbl Augenheilkd*, 227(10), pp.819-826
 32. Aykut, S., Caner, C., Ozkan, G., Ali, C., Tugba, A., Zeynep, G. and Taner, C. (2010). Mupirocin application at the exit site in peritoneal dialysis patients: five years of experience. *Renal Failure*, 32(3), pp.356-361.
 33. Jackson JM, Fu JJ, Almekinder JL. A randomized, investigator-blinded trial to assess the antimicrobial efficacy of a benzoyl peroxide 5%/ clindamycin phosphate 1% gel compared with a clindamycin phosphate 1.2%/tretinoin 0.025% gel in the topical treatment of acne vulgaris. *J Drugs Dermatol* 2010; 9(2), pp.131-136.
 34. de Leeuw, J., van der Beek, N., Bjerring, P. and Martino Neumann, H. (2010). Photodynamic therapy of acne vulgaris using 5-aminolevulinic acid 0.5% liposomal spray and intense pulsed light in combination with topical keratolytic agents. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*, 24(4), pp.460-469.
 35. He, L., Ta, C. and Miño de Kaspar, H. (2009). One-day application of topical moxifloxacin 0.5% to select for fluoroquinolone-resistant coagulase-negative Staphylococcus. *Journal of Cataract & Refractive Surgery*, 35(10), pp.1715-1718.
 36. Dhawan SS. (2009). Comparison of 2 clindamycin 1%-benzoyl peroxide 5% topical gels used once daily in the management of acne vulgaris. *Cutis*, 83(5), pp.265-72.
 37. Johnson DW, Clark C, Isbel NM, et al. (2009). The honeypot study protocol: a randomized controlled trial of exit-site application of medihoney antibacterial wound gel for the prevention of catheter-associated infections in peritoneal dialysis patients. *Perit Dial Int*. 29(3), pp.303-309.
 38. Daly, J. (2010). Decontamination of the Digestive Tract and Oropharynx in ICU Patients. *Yearbook of Surgery*, 2010, pp.209-210.
 39. Lipsky, B., Holroyd, K. and Zasloff, M. (2008). Topical versus Systemic Antimicrobial Therapy for Treating Mildly Infected Diabetic Foot Ulcers: A Randomized, Controlled, Double-Blinded, Multicenter Trial of Pexiganan Cream. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 47(12), pp.1537-1545.
 40. Denis, F., Chaumeil, C., Goldschmidt, P., Delval, L., Pouliquen, P., Cochereau, I., Chainier, D. and De Barbeyrac, B. (2008). Microbiologic Efficacy of 3-day Treatment with Azithromycin 1.5% Eyedrops for Purulent Bacterial Conjunctivitis. *European Journal of Ophthalmology*, 18(6), pp.858-868.